

Transceiver Count Reduction in Filterless Metro-Aggregation Networks Using DSCM

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Abstract—This study investigates the impact that Point-to-Multipoint (P2MP), traffic growth, and optical aggregation have on the performance of the optical systems and on the necessary hardware required to ensure connectivity across the full network. We leverage the examples of realistic topologies provided by Telecom Italia (TIM) to generalize the network characteristics and allow for statistical analysis of horseshoe-based metro-aggregation scenarios.

By comparing the necessary hardware (i.e., number of optical transceivers) in Point-to-Point (P2P) and in P2MP operation, our investigation reveals the extent to which Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing (DSCM) in combination with optical aggregation allows to reduce the number of pluggable units that need to be deployed. In the simulations, under the assumption of a pay-as-you-grow provisioning strategy, we observe a reduction in transceivers in the 33%–45% range depending on the aggregation level and traffic volume after 10 years of operation. In addition to this, we are able to calculate the maximum required cost of the DSCM-capable transceivers with respect to more traditional P2P solutions to produce cost-effective deployments. These results, presented as a function of traffic volume, level of optical aggregation, and relative cost with respect to P2P transceivers, provide an understanding of the overall cost of acquiring DSCM-based pluggable units, and demonstrate that, even though the price point might be higher, the reduction in terms of hardware due to adopting a P2MP approach compensates this aspect and can still allow for the deployment to be more cost-effective.

Index Terms—filterless optical networks, digital subcarrier multiplexing, optical aggregation, techno-economic analysis, point-to-multipoint transmission

I. INTRODUCTION

Optical networks have grown over the years from a mere connection between two remote sites to a complete infrastructure that can support multiple applications [1], cope with ever-increasing traffic demands [2], and offer flexibility at different levels (e.g., software and optical reconfiguration, adjustment of hardware parameters, etc.) [3], [4], while at the same time aiming to fulfill requirements regarding power consumption [5]. This evolution does not come for free, however, as telecom operators must upgrade their networks with new hardware that supports these new features. Here,

network planning and deployment strategies determine how and when the financial resources should be spent. For instance, with an upfront acquisition of the necessary hardware (i.e., at year 0), operators are able to reduce excess capacity [6], but this requires a large investment at a single point in time; not to mention a precise assessment of the traffic growth for the upcoming years. An alternative to this would be a pay-as-you-grow strategy, where the operators react to the evolution of the network, acquiring optical components as they become necessary.

In the metro-aggregation domain of an operator's network, P2MP as a communication paradigm, enabled by Digital Subcarriers (DSCs), has been presented as a suitable approach to address several of the aspects that were mentioned [7]. By principle, not only does DSCM allow operators to design networks with flexibility at the forefront [8], [9], but also to address efficiency in terms of hardware resources and, therefore, Capital Expenditure (CAPEX).

While previous works have provided insight into the flexibility, power consumption, and hardware provisioning in filterless networks [8], [9], these analyses focused on specific network scenarios. For more general conclusions regarding the performance and techno-economic perspective in the metro-aggregation domain, it is fundamental to carry out numerical investigations that consider statistical randomization of the network topologies, as well as their characteristics. Our present study quantifies the impact that optical aggregation and traffic growth have on the system performance and on the amount of necessary hardware (i.e. number of pluggable transceivers) according to a pay-as-you-grow approach. In addition, by comparing P2MP networks to more traditional P2P deployments, we strive to provide an understanding of the necessary costs of DSCM-capable transceivers to result in deployments that are competitive to those using P2P solutions in terms of cost-efficiency.

This article has been organized into three main blocks. The first one, section II presents the general scenario for the filterless metro-aggregation networks, as well as the underlying

assumptions for our investigation. Subsequently, section III summarizes the simulation results. Here, in section III-A, we begin by discussing the Optical Signal-to-Noise-Ratio (OSNR) analysis of a P2MP pay-as-you-grow metro-aggregation network and the implications of optical aggregation on the system performance. Section III-B offers insight into the hardware aspect of a network's operation, highlighting how transceiver count might be reduced by adopting a DSCM-based P2MP strategy. Then, section III-C provides tangible estimations regarding DSCM transceivers to be able to compete with more traditional P2P solutions in terms of cost. Finally, section IV draws our conclusions.

II. NETWORK SCENARIO

Fig. 1: (a) General topology of the networks. (b) Probability of the number of leaf nodes in a sublink. (c) Probability Density Functions (PDFs) corresponding to the fiber segment distance between nodes (green) and to the leaf nodes' traffic demands (orange).

To provide insight into the dynamics of filterless metro-aggregation scenarios, we developed a simulator to create networks according to a horseshoe topology, where multiple branches (sublinks) connect to a single aggregator node (hub node). In turn, each sublink in a network comprises a given number of leaf nodes with their own particular traffic demands. The network and node designs used in this study resemble the ones in [8]: parallel fiber paths for uplink and downlink, passive couplers to add/drop optical channels, and amplifiers at the leaf nodes to compensate for link losses and to adjust the power of the optical signals. In our research, DSCs are polarization-multiplexed 4 GBd 16-QAM Nyquist channels with a corresponding net data rate of 25 Gb/s [7], [10].

For a generalized analysis, we constructed the networks randomly, extracting the design parameters from probability distributions, which were defined based on examples of representative optical metro-aggregation networks provided by TIM. From a selection of 15 networks with a total of 46 sublinks and 187 leaf nodes, in order to re-construct them in our simulator, we extracted descriptive data by means of an exploratory analysis: number of parallel horseshoes, number of leaf nodes per sublink, traffic per leaf node, and the fiber segment's distance between any possible pair of nodes. A generic description of the virtual networks is illustrated in Fig. 1 (a), where n and N denote the number of horseshoes and local number of leaf nodes, respectively. Furthermore, the letters A and B indicate the main and protection nodes respectively. Through our analysis, we noticed that the networks are composed of 2–4 sublinks, where the number of leaf nodes follows the probability distribution depicted in Fig. 1 (b). To complement the information concerning the network architecture, we have summarized the distance between leaf nodes and their corresponding traffic demands in Fig. 1 (c). With regards to the fiber links, the distance of the individual fiber segments has been capped to a maximum value of 80 km, as we do not want to include additional amplifiers other than those units at the leaf nodes. Traffic is then assumed to grow on a year-by-year basis over 10 years, following a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) with values ranging from 10% to 40%. Due to the statistical approach of this work, to provide an evaluation that can serve as a generalized statement about the operation of metro-aggregation networks, we have performed this analysis over 1000 independent network scenarios.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Optical Performance

Fig. 2: Schematic diagrams for a horseshoe-based network topology in (a) P2P and (b) P2MP operation.

Optical system based on DSCM have the possibility of being operated as P2P links or operated using a P2MP scheme.

In the traditional P2P configuration, illustrated in Fig. 2 (a), the transceivers at the hub nodes communicate with book-ended counterparts (i.e., one-to-one) at the leaf nodes. In the depiction, this is represented by how the circles of different colors beneath the hub node A are connected to particular leaf nodes in the horseshoe topology. On the other hand, P2MP configuration refers to a scenario where transceiver units at the hub node are capable of communicating with multiple leaf nodes simultaneously. In this context, in contrast with P2P, Fig. 2 (b) presents P2MP as having a single source at the hub node—represented by the single red rectangle—that connects to the four leaf nodes in the example, where colors are also used to indicate the traffic source/destination. With P2MP in mind, we have previously introduced the concept of ‘level(s) of aggregation’ to represent the degree to which hardware resources can be shared in horseshoe networks, and which is defined by the following expression [8]:

$$\text{Agg. Level} = \frac{1}{C_s} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{C_s} \text{Agg}_s; \quad (1)$$

where Agg_s represents how many sublinks are being combined and served by a single source¹ at the hub node, and C_s denotes the number of combinations required to guarantee full connectivity to the network. According to this figure of merit regarding optical aggregation, the higher the value, the more sublinks are combined and served by common sources at the hub node. In this regard, by aggregating the traffic of multiple leaf nodes (and horseshoes) and establishing connectivity with higher-capacity DSCM-capable transceivers, we can effectively reduce the number of pluggables that are required to ensure full connectivity at the physical layer, which

¹Despite mention of a ‘single’ source, this can represent multiple transceivers. It depends on the traffic volume the units at the hub have to address among one or multiple horseshoes.

might lead to savings in terms of CAPEX depending on the type of network. To exemplify this concept, Fig. 3 (a) shows different ways a four-sublink network can be operated at a logical level in terms of connections.

Before carrying out a techno-economic analysis, however, it is important to understand the operating conditions of the network. For this reason, we calculated the OSNR evolution across the network for both the downlink and uplink transmission directions based on the necessary hardware (i.e., transceivers) to cover the growing traffic demands at a given point in time. Following a pay-as-you-grow deployment strategy, once the capacity of the available pluggable transceivers is exceeded, an additional pluggable with a suitable capacity will be introduced at the corresponding location in the network. For reference, depending on the scenario, both 100 Gb/s and 400 Gb/s pluggables can be deployed at the hub node, while only 100 Gb/s units will be used for the leaf nodes.

To represent the optical performance of the network, we calculate the OSNR margin. This metric results from comparing the OSNR of a given fiber connection to the transceiver’s requirements for error-free operation [10]. In this regard, we identify the limiting performance among the sublink combinations (i.e., lowest OSNR value) and use it to describe the overall performance of the network scenario. In this way, we can perform a preliminary evaluation whether a network can be realized and only consider scenarios where the OSNR margin ≥ 0 dB. The performance of the network for different growth rates as a function of years-in-operation is depicted in Fig. 3 (b). As time goes on, we observe how changes in hardware affect the OSNR margin of the network, since—for example—additional passive components introduce extra losses, power values of the DSCs have to be modified, and amplifiers are readjusted; this all leads to a systemic worsening of the overall performance.

By comparing the categorization based on levels of aggre-

Fig. 3: (a) Example of a four-horseshoe network showing sublink combinations for various levels of aggregation. The box with ‘×’ represents a coupler/splitter with equal ratio among its inputs/outputs, respectively. (b) Average OSNR margin value across the years as a function of the type of network and level of aggregation. The number preceding the ‘H’ indicates the number of horseshoes in a network and the number in parenthesis, the level of aggregation.

gation, which depends on the number of available sublinks in the network, with the results shown in Fig. 3 (b), we can notice an inverse relation: higher aggregation results in worse optical performances. This is because additional passive components would have to be deployed (i.e., extra power losses), more optical signals will have to be combined (i.e., power equalization and noise addition), and it is increasingly likely that one of the newly-considered sublinks has more leaf nodes and a corresponding worse OSNR margin. For these reasons, on average, higher levels of aggregation lead to lower OSNR margin values.

B. Transceiver Deployment

When considering a pay-as-you-grow provisioning approach, operators deploy new hardware to the network nodes as the need arises. Figure 4 shows how many transceiver units—regardless of their capacity—are required on average to guarantee coping with the increasing traffic volume. The data have been normalized with respect to the number of leaf nodes in the simulated scenarios to allow for networks of different sizes to be compared fairly and are depicted as a function of the aggregation level for the P2MP implementations.

Fig. 4: Number of transceiver units per leaf node across the years as a function of the aggregation level and CAGR for a pay-as-you-grow approach.

At the start of life, with traditional P2P solutions, we have an average of two pluggable units per leaf node (i.e., one at the leaf node and one at the hub node). In contrast, by switching over a P2MP, we are capable of reducing this ratio, since the transceivers at the hub can communicate with multiple leaf nodes simultaneously. By comparing the number of pluggable units required for P2P (data in black) and P2MP (data in color) operation, we can calculate a reduction rate in terms of hardware. These values, as a function of the level of aggregation and year-over-year CAGR, have been plotted for the tenth year of operation in Fig. 5.

From the plots, we can observe that in ‘low-traffic conditions’—for which a value of 10% is a valid proxy—there is potential for large savings, as the P2MP approach and DSCM allow to combine the functions of multiple endpoints into a single pluggable unit. Conversely, as the traffic volume increases, the effectiveness of optical aggregation goes

Fig. 5: Reduction percentage in terms of transceivers (at year 10) as a function of aggregation level and CAGR for a pay-as-you-grow approach.

down, since the transceivers at the hub are mostly addressing the demands of a smaller subset of leaf nodes.

C. Cost of 100 Gb/s DSCM-capable Transceivers

However, when comparing P2MP deployments with more traditional P2P networks, the number of pluggables is an unfair comparison metric. We should also consider enhancements to the technology (e.g., low-cost coherent solutions, low-power Digital Signal Processing (DSP), etc.) and consequently different transceiver costs. Hence, we should change our metric to a more tangible: the hardware acquisition cost. Taking our previous analysis and filtering it by this metric, we can state the required cost that is needed for DSCM-based transceivers, so that a deployment of these pluggables is more cost-effective than using a P2P approach. In this regard, based on our previous knowledge of the necessary number of transceiver units, we can define the following equation:

$$N_{P2MP-400G} \cdot C_{P2MP-400G} + N_{P2MP-100G} \cdot C_{P2MP-100G} \leq N_{P2P-100G} \cdot C_{P2P-100G}; \quad (2)$$

where N_x and C_x represent the number of pluggable units in the network and their corresponding acquisition cost, respectively. In this context, x denotes a given type of transceiver.

By normalizing with respect to the cost of the P2P 100-Gb/s unit, we can convey the different P2MP terms in the equation to be related to it. The equation would look as follows:

$$\frac{N_{P2MP-400G} \cdot C_{P2MP-400G}}{C_{P2P-100G}} + \frac{N_{P2MP-100G} \cdot C_{P2MP-100G}}{C_{P2P-100G}} \leq N_{P2P-100G}; \quad (3)$$

To simplify Eq. 3, the cost ratio between the P2P and P2MP transceivers can be expressed through summary variables in the following way:

$$N_{P2MP-400G} \cdot \alpha + N_{P2MP-100G} \cdot \beta \leq N_{P2P-100G}; \quad (4)$$

where α and β denote values to represent the acquisition cost of the P2MP 400-Gb/s and 100-Gb/s transceivers, respectively,

Fig. 6: Average maximum possible relative cost for a DSCM-capable 100 Gb/s transceiver to guarantee that the pluggables’ overall cost of deployment (at year 10) is as expensive as deploying 100 Gb/s single-carrier solutions. Without loss of generality, relative unit costs are presented with respect to the cost of a single-carrier 100 Gb/s transceiver (solid line at value of 1), as a function of the scenario’s CAGR and the cost of a 400 Gb/s module with DSCM.

compared to that of the P2P 100-Gb/s variant. To allow for realistic and competitive implementations, α has been specified as a value ranging from 3 to 5, meaning that a DSCM-capable pluggable with a capacity of 400 Gb/s could cost between 3 and 5 times the amount of a P2P 100 Gb/s pluggable unit.

Consequently, Equation 4 can help us express the necessary cost for a 100-Gb/s DSCM-based transceiver with respect to that of a P2P one operating at the same data rate. Figure 6 summarizes these calculations as a function of multiple conditions (at year 10): traffic growth, level of optical aggregation, and relative cost of the 400-Gb/s unit. In this graph, since the analysis is performed in with respect to the P2P units, values lower than ‘1’ indicate that the 100-Gb/s P2MP solution must be cheaper than its P2P counterpart for the complete transceiver deployment to be competitive in terms of cost. On the other hand, values higher than ‘1’ inform us that there is some margin for DSCM-based solutions; they can be slightly more expensive than P2P and still manage to reduce the overall cost across the network thanks to the P2MP scheme.

In addition, by closely inspecting Fig. 6, we can identify several behavioral trends that explain the underlying mechanisms of the cost relation. For example, in every depicted scenario, it can be seen how the relative cost for the P2MP pluggable is proportional to the aggregation level. In other words, by increasing optical aggregation, we reduce the overall number of transceivers that are required to cope with the network’s traffic demands; this, in turn, implies that the fewer transceivers there are, the more they can cost and still keep deployment as expensive as for P2P units. These data points are represented by the color-coded markers in Fig. 6. Therefore, the area below the curve that joins the colored markers represents cost values where a DSCM-based P2MP deployment makes sense in terms of cost-efficiency, should we focus solely on transceivers. Then, by changing α , which describes the relative cost between the high-speed 400-Gb/s DSCM module and the reference P2P solution, we can perceive how the curve denoting the cost-efficiency threshold

for P2MP shifts accordingly: to be competitive with high-cost 400-Gb/s units, the 100-Gb/s pluggables must compensate by being cheaper. Finally, our last observation is related to optical aggregation and traffic volume: optical aggregation offers diminishing returns as traffic increases; namely, the gap between an aggregation level of 1 and an aggregation level of 4 grows smaller. The reason behind this is the fact that with higher data demands, the effectiveness of a P2MP scheme with only 16 DSCs decreases, as the communication between the hub node and leaf node transceivers tends to exhibit a behavior resembling that of P2P.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this article, we have investigated the relation between traffic growth, represented by a year-over-year CAGR value, optical aggregation, network performance, and necessary hardware (i.e., transceiver units) in DSCM-based filterless metro-aggregation scenario with a pay-as-you-grow strategy. Our analysis is predicated around the use of horseshoe topologies, constructed randomly according to the properties and characteristics of realistic examples provided by TIM. Our generalized results demonstrate the advantages of P2MP over P2P operation with regard to the number of transceivers necessary to ensure full physical-layer connectivity across the complete network. At the tenth year of operation, P2MP necessitates 33%–44% fewer transceivers depending on the amount of traffic and level of optical aggregation. Furthermore, based on our simulations, we provide a cost-oriented guide to determine the conditions under which P2MP deployments predicated on the use of DSCs are able to be more cost-effective than P2P solutions at the transceiver-level, without the need for additional active optical components. For example, in low-traffic conditions (10% CAGR) with expensive high-speed pluggables ($\alpha = 5$), aggregating more than half of the sublinks allows for the DSCM-capable 100 Gb/s modules to have a price point 15% higher compared to their P2P counterpart and still be more cost-efficient. On the other hand, a very

high traffic volume (40% CAGR) requires either cheap high-speed pluggables ($\alpha \leq 3.5$) or a minimum degree of optical aggregation (e.g., an aggregation level ≥ 1.5), or a combination thereof to provide sufficient cost margin for producing and manufacturing the optical modules.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Carlos Castro, João Pedro, Marco Quagliotti, Emilio Riccardi, André Souza, Mohammad Hosseini, and Antonio Napoli gratefully acknowledge support from the European Union's Horizon RIA research and innovation program under SEASON (G.A. 101096120).

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